

SYNTHESIS OF N1-[2-(4 H-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-4-YL) ACETYL]-(1-ADAMANTYL)-4-BENZOHYDRAZIDE AS A POTENTIAL ANTICANCER DRUG**Klimko Yu.***PhD in Chemistry, Senior Lecturer**Department of Organic Chemistry and Technology of Organic Substances
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National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute"***Abstract**

The 1,2,4-triazole ring and azaglycine are two pharmacologically significant structural units associated with cytotoxic activity. In particular, the azaglycine scaffold exhibits increased affinity for the enzyme cathepsin B, an established molecular target in breast cancer. Accordingly, a product (3) containing an adamantyl substituent at position 4 of the phenyl ring was synthesized, significantly increasing the lipophilicity of the substrate.

Keywords 1, 2, 4-Triazole, Azaglycine, Cathepsin B, Anticancer, Adamantane.

Introduction

Breast cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer deaths among women worldwide, with a higher incidence rate observed in older adults and postmenopausal women [1, 2]. The development of new anticancer drugs remains a major focus of medicinal chemistry, and heterocyclic compounds have emerged as promising candidates.

Due to their ability to modulate various molecular targets associated with cancer, several FDA-approved anticancer drugs, including tucatinib, alpelisib, capmatinib, pralsetinib, and darolutamide, contain heterocyclic rings in their structures.

Among various heterocycles, the 1,2,4-triazole system has attracted considerable attention due to its potent cytotoxic properties. Other important activities of 1,2,4-triazoles include antimicrobial, antioxidant, antituberculosis, antiviral, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant, and antidepressant activities [3–5]. In the field of oncology, triazole derivatives are actively investigated as next-generation anticancer drugs. Their anticancer activity is mediated by various mechanisms, including enzyme inhibition, microtubule destabilization, and activation of cell cycle arrest. The triazole ring binds tightly to receptors via hydrogen bonds, dipole–dipole interactions, and π -stacking, which contributes to high binding affinity and therapeutic potential [6–11].

One promising approach to the development of triazole-based anticancer agents is the creation of complex hybrids combining the 1,2,4-triazole core with other anticancer pharmacophores such as coumarin, phthalazine, pyrimidine, pyridine, piperidine, quinoxaline, quinazoline, thiadiazine, and indole [12–14]. Numerous studies have also highlighted the therapeutic potential of 1,2,4-triazole amides. Tukey et al. synthesized 1,2,4-triazole-narylamide hybrids and evaluated the anticancer activity against a multidrug-resistant human breast adenocarcinoma cell line (MDA-MB-231) [15]. Another study reported the synthesis of 1,2,4-thiadiazole-1,2,4-triazole derivatives containing an amide functional group, which demonstrated anticancer activity against breast cancer (MCF-7 and MDAMB-231), lung cancer (A549), and prostate cancer (DU-145) cell

lines [16]. Tom et al. synthesized a series of thirty N-acyl-1,2,4-triazoles and evaluated their antimalarial activity [17].

Azaglycine is a synthetic analogue of glycine in which the alpha carbon is replaced by nitrogen, resulting in a hydrazide-like structure (-NH-NH-CO). Incorporation of the azaglycinyl (Agly) moiety into the peptide structure enhances conformational stability and increases hydrogen bonding capacity, thereby improving biological activity and resistance to enzymatic degradation [18, 19]. This structural modification has been shown to facilitate the design of highly potent and selective cathepsin B inhibitors by constraining the peptide backbone in a kinked conformation that facilitates target binding [20]. In preclinical cancer studies, azaglycine has demonstrated moderate antiproliferative effects [21]. Despite the extensive study of triazole-based hybrids and the pharmacological significance of azaglycinyl units, the systematic evaluation of the cytotoxicity of molecular systems integrating both structural motifs remains largely unexplored. [22] reported the cytotoxic potential of 4-amino-5-substituted 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol derivatives against a breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) and emphasized the therapeutic importance of the 1,2,4-triazole core in the development of anticancer drugs. Based on this logic, in the present study, a benzoyl-azaglycinamide moiety containing an adamantyl substituent is introduced into the 1,2,4-triazole structure (Fig. 2), combining two complementary pharmacophoric units in a single molecular structure. The benzoyl group containing 1-adamantyl was chosen to enhance lipophilicity and facilitate π - π stacking interactions with aromatic residues in the target binding site, potentially improving biological activity.

This hybridization strategy aims to combine the electronic and binding versatility of the triazole core with the conformational and hydrogen bonding advantages of the azaglycine moiety.

The synthesis protocol is shown in Scheme 1.

1,2,4-Triazole (0.01 mol, 1 equiv) was dissolved in dichloromethane (50 mL) with constant stirring at room temperature (25 °C). Triethylamine (2 mL, ca. 1.5 equiv) was added, followed by dropwise addition of ethyl chloroacetate (0.01 mol, 1 equiv). The reaction

mixture was stirred for 3–5 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was washed with cold water to remove residual triethylamine. The resulting solid was dried under vacuum to obtain 1,2,4-triazole ethyl ester (1) [23].

Synthesis of substituted benzohydrazide (2): The substituted benzohydrazide was prepared by esterification of substituted benzoic acid followed by hydrazinolysis.

Preparation of 4-(1-adamantyl)methyl Experimental

1,2,4-Triazole, ethyl acetoacetate, triethylamine, substituted benzoic acid, hydrazine hydrate, methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, concentrated sulfuric acid, and carbon tetrachloride were purchased from Makrochim (Ukraine) and Aldrich.

All chemical reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification.

Reaction progress was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel plates using appropriate solvent systems. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were obtained using a Bruker FTIR spectrometer. Spectrophotometer (cm⁻¹). NMR spectra were recorded in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-d₆) on Bruker 400 MHz and Joel 400 MHz instruments. Mass spectra (m/z) were obtained using an Apexex mass spectrometer (300800.D) Синтез этилового эфира 1,2,4-триазола (1).

benzoate: Substituted benzoic acid (0.1 mol, 1 equiv) was dissolved in excess methanol, and concentrated sulfuric acid (5.7 mL, catalytic amount) was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 65°C for 4–6 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was poured into ice water. The resulting methyl 4-(1-adamantyl)benzoate was extracted with carbon tetrachloride. The organic layer was separated, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate, and concentrated under reduced pressure. The yield is quantitative.

Preparation of substituted benzohydrazide:

The resulting methyl ester (0.1 mol, 1 equiv) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (0.15 mol, 1.5 equiv) in ethanol (5.7 mL) for 4–6 h. Excess ethanol was removed under vacuum, and the crystalline benzohydrazide was filtered. The product was washed with cold ethanol and dried to obtain the substituted benzohydrazide (2). Yield 92%.

Synthesis of N1-[2-(4 H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)acetyl]-4-(1-adamantyl)benzohydrazide (3): A mixture of 1,2,4-triazole ethyl ester (1) (0.01 mol, 1 eq.), substituted benzohydrazide (0.02 mol, 2 eq.) was dissolved in ethanol (50 mL) and refluxed for 4–6 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator. The resulting solid was collected and purified by recrystallization from a mixture of ethanol and water. Yield 89%.

Scheme 1. Synthesis protocol.

Physical and spectral data of intermediate compound (2).

4-(1-Adamantyl)benzohydrazide (2). Off-white solid, M.P. 193–195 °C, Rf: 0.61 (ethyl acetate: hexane: methanol 3:1:4). FT-IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3309.42 (N-H str), 1661.83 (C = O str); ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3\text{-d}_6$, 400 MHz) δ (ppm): 1.48, 1.92, 1.68 (m, 15H), 4.58 (s, 2 H, NH_2), 6.91–7.82(m, 4 H, Ar-H), 10.21 (s, 1H, CO-NH).

Physical and spectral data of the final compounds (3).

N1-(2-(4 H-1,2,4-Triazol-4-yl)acetyl)-4-(1-adamantyl)benzohydrazide (3). M.P. 211–213 °C Rf: 0.80 (ethyl acetate: hexane: methanol 2:1:1); FT-IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3380.13 (N-H str), 2981.00 (C-H str, aromatic), 1665.44 (C = O str), 1497.46 (C-N str), 1190.63 (Ar-CO str); ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3\text{-d}_6$, 400 MHz) δ (ppm): 1.48, 1.92, 1.68 (m, 15H), 4.6 (s, 2 H, CH_2), 7.2–7.4 (m, 4 H, Ar-H), 8.5 (s, 2 H, CH of 1,2,4-triazole), 10.2 (s, 1H, NH-CO), 10.8 (s, 1H, NH-CO-Ar); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3\text{-d}_6$, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 29.0 (γ , CH, AdC), 31.6 (α , C, AdC), 37.5 (δ , CH_2 , AdC), 43.3 (β , CH_2 , AdC), 48.7 (CH_2), 125.6 (2 x ArC), 128.2 (2 x ArC), 129.8 (ArC), 131.1 (ArC), 145.2 (2 x TrC), 164.4 (CO), 164.9 (CO); MS (EI) m/z: 379[M] $^{+}$.

Results and discussion

1,2,4-Triazole ethyl ester (1) was condensed with substituted benzohydrazide (2) to afford the title compound (Scheme 1). The benzohydrazide (2) were obtained by treating benzoic acid esters with hydrazine. Subsequently, the reaction between 1,2,4-triazole ethyl ester and substituted benzohydrazide led to the formation of the title compound (3). Both reactions involve the nucleophilic substitution mechanism. The structures of the final compounds were confirmed by spectral analysis. The ^1H NMR spectrum displayed characteristic peaks ranging from 4.2 to 4.6 (s, CH_2), 6.8–7.8 (m, Ar-H), and 10.0–10.8.0.8 (s, NH). In the ^{13}C NMR spectra, methylene carbons were observed at δ around 40, phenyl carbons were found with δ values in the range of 114–150, and amide carbons were observed at around δ 164.

Conclusion

The present study describes the synthesis of a novel of N1-[2-(4 H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl) acetyl]-4-(1-adamantyl)benzohydrazides (3), incorporating both the 1,2,4-triazole scaffold and the benzoylazaglycinyl pharmacophore, which are well-recognized structural motifs in anticancer drug design.

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